

CTI-GEN: A Framework for Generating STIX 2.1 Compliant CTI Using Generative AI

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Abstract—Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) enables organisations and individuals to gather knowledge about the cyber-attack landscape. This work presents a framework, CTI-GEN, for generating CTI in the Structured Threat Information eXpression (STIX) format from unstructured textual reports. The framework leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) to automate the generation of CTI in STIX. The framework consists of six components, each designed to complement and correct the previous ones, and uses detailed prompt engineering procedures to guide the model in generating CTI in STIX. To this end, the STIX schema was preprocessed to simplify its complex and redundant interdependencies so that to be leveraged it effectively. CTI-GEN achieved an F1-Score of 81% in generating relevant objects from the text, 57% in the generation of relationships between the objects, and, importantly, a precision of 96% in the assignment of values to attributes in the CTI objects. This work presents the first approach to generate complete and error-free CTI using LLMs and the full spectrum of STIX.

Index Terms—Generative AI, Large Language Models, Cybersecurity, Information Security, Cyber Threat Intelligence, Threat Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) is a critical component of cybersecurity that aids in risk management, threat prevention, detection, and incident response [1], [2]. The Structured Threat Information Expression (STIX) language provides a standardized format for representing and sharing CTI to ensure interoperability across security tools and organizations [3]. However, generating accurate and comprehensive CTI in STIX remains a resource-intensive process that requires significant human effort and expertise. Current tools and efforts provide limited guidance for transforming unstructured text reports into valid and structured CTI, which leads to inefficiencies and inconsistencies in the produced CTI [4].

Specifically, existing CTI generation approaches often fail to produce STIX-compliant CTI that fully leverages the richness of the STIX language. Many research efforts have focused primarily on simple Indicators of Compromise (IOCs), such as IP addresses and domain names, and have neglected the broader context and interconnections among threat actors, attack patterns, malware families, and related entities [5]. In addition, these approaches frequently generate incomplete or syntactically incorrect STIX objects, thereby omitting essential

attributes and relationships. As a result, publicly available CTI is often fragmented, inaccurate, or limited to a small subset of STIX-defined entities, which reduces its practical utility in cybersecurity operations [4].

To address the forenamed shortcomings of automated CTI generation approaches, this work introduces CTI-GEN, a novel framework that automates the extraction, validation, and refinement of CTI from unstructured text while ensuring STIX compliance. It consists of six components: an initial CTI generator that employs prompt engineering and three-shot learning to produce STIX-formatted CTI, a completeness and syntactic evaluator that checks CTI against a simplified STIX schema, and an updatable CTI generator that enhances the initial output by adding missing attributes and verifying relationships. A relationship updating editor augments the relationships between the objects and ensures correct object connections, while a hallucination checker removes inaccuracies by validating CTI elements against the source text. Finally, a syntactic CTI validator detects and corrects any remaining structural errors using a Python-based validation approach. By streamlining STIX and refining the CTI generation process, CTI-GEN improves the accuracy, consistency, and compliance of automated CTI production.

The CTI-GEN framework is demonstrated by using OpenAI’s GPT-4o model [6], [7] with specific prompt engineering instructions to generate complete (i.e., all relevant objects in a text are extracted), with many relationships, precise values, and syntactically error-free STIX-compliant CTI that contains all predefined relationships of the STIX schema as well as precise values. GPT-4o was chosen as it is one of the most widely used LLMs [8]. Similarly, STIX was selected as the focus of this work given its wide adoption [9], [10]. STIX represents CTI through structured objects and their relationships. These objects fall into three primary categories: *STIX Domain Objects (SDOs)*, *STIX Cyber Observable Objects (SCOs)*, and *STIX Relationship Objects (SROs)*. SDOs include 19 object types that capture high-level threat intelligence, such as malware, attack patterns, and threat actors. SCOs comprise 18 objects representing low-level IOCs, including IP addresses, domain names, file hashes, and other technical artefacts. SROs define relationships between these objects, establishing links such as

associating a file hash with a malware entity or connecting a threat actor to an attack pattern. Finally, each STIX object follows a structured schema containing both required and optional attributes. In this work, all three objects are used.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to both generate and evaluate CTI generated by LLMs against the full spectrum of STIX. In addition, this study is the first to demonstrate that LLMs powered with well-grafted prompts can generate CTI containing all relevant to the input, objects of STIX. Although the framework automates the generation and validation of CTI, human evaluation of the results is essential for continuously refining and updating its functionality.

The main contributions of this work are:

- Generation of a complete and error-free STIX compliant CTI using Generative AI.
- Preprocessing of the STIX 2.1 schema to transform it into a more comprehensive and friendly version.
- Full utilization of the STIX 2.1 for generating CTI, including all objects and relationships specified.
- A detailed automated evaluation of the required and optional attributes of the objects in a CTI, including syntactic checks, against the STIX 2.1 schema.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section II presents work related to IDS rule generation. Section III details the proposed framework. Section IV describes an implementation instance of the proposed framework and Section V presents the experimental results on this implementation instance. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Various research efforts have addressed CTI generation through a wide range of techniques, from manual approaches to semi-automated and fully automated techniques, with or without reliance on STIX. For example, in [11], the authors presented a framework called CyTIME that generates CTI from heterogeneous data in STIX format. Then, the CTI was transformed into security rules for Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) such as Suricata, Snort, and YARA. The CTI and IDS rules were generated using a manual approach with a small number of STIX objects.

In another work [12], the author introduced TIMiner, an automated framework designed for CTI extraction and sharing based on social media. This approach addresses two key challenges in CTI: identifying unseen types of IoCs and automatically generating categorised CTI with domain tags (e.g., finance, government, education). Named Entity Recognition (NER) and BiLSTM-CRF models were used for the recognition of IoCs, and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the categorisation of IoCs. The extraction of the CTI did not follow the structure format of STIX. In [13], the authors introduced INTIME, an automated CTI gathering and analysis framework. They aimed to collect, rank, extract, integrate, and share CTI from diverse sources, such as the clear web, deep web, dark web, social media, and structured security databases. The paper used different automated methods for

CTI gathering. Automated ranking and classification of cybersecurity content was performed using word embeddings and NLP methods. IoCs, vulnerabilities, malware, and exploits extraction was performed with NER- and Regex-based models. STIX was not used for representing the extracted information.

In [14], the authors introduced aCTIon, a structured CTI information extraction tool that leverages LLMs to improve CTI extraction from unstructured sources. They structured the CTI using the STIX format; however, they leveraged a small portion of the relevant objects and relationships. A study close to ours is the one in [15], where a hybrid Artificial Intelligence [AI] approach combining rule-based, Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), and LLMs was used for entity and relation extraction to generate CTI in STIX. Although they claimed that they extracted all the objects and relationships of STIX, they only extracted SDOs and not SCOS.

Contrary to existing research, this study focuses on generating CTI by leveraging all the objects and relationships in the STIX 2.1 framework. In addition, this work provides an automated evaluation of CTI objects against a preprocessing version of STIX 2.1, providing complete and error-free CTI.

III. CTI-GEN FRAMEWORK

The proposed CTI-GEN framework is designed to generate CTI in STIX 2.1 (hereinafter referred to as STIX) using Generative AI. As depicted in Figure 1, the framework comprises six components. The *Initial CTI Generator*, *Updatable CTI Generator*, *Relationships Updating Editor*, and *Hallucination Checker* components use distinct prompt engineering procedures to guide the generation and subsequent refinement and enhancement of the generated CTI. The *CTI Completeness and Syntactic evaluator* is a code-based component that verifies the structural validity and completeness of the initially generated CTI, while the *Syntactic CTI Validator* ensures that the final CTI is free of syntactic errors.

A. CTI-GEN Initial CTI Generator Component

The goal of this component is to convert an unstructured textual report into an initial version of STIX-compliant CTI, leveraging Generative AI capabilities. In particular, the component uses the GPT-4o model which receives as input a textual report containing cyber threat information, along with detailed instructions defining the expected CTI output. These instructions are provided via two prompts: the *system prompt* and the *user prompt*. The *system prompt* includes the descriptions of all STIX objects to reinforce the model's understanding of the STIX SDOs, SCOs and SROs so that it can recognise and extract them from the textual report.

The *user prompt* contains the specific textual report from which the CTI is to be generated. It also contains three input-output examples, where each input consists of a textual report, and the corresponding output is the expected CTI in STIX format. These examples serve as direct references to guide the model in correctly structuring the generated CTI according to STIX. In addition, the user prompt includes detailed instructions that explicitly direct the model to extract

Fig. 1. CTI-GEN Framework

only entities explicitly mentioned in the input text and map them to corresponding STIX objects. This ensures that the model does not introduce inferred, unrelated, or hallucinated entities and does not generate additional properties for STIX objects beyond those present in the input.

B. CTI-GEN Completeness & Syntactic Evaluator Component

This component is designed to verify the presence of all required attributes of each STIX object, to provide information about the optional ones, and to identify syntactic errors. The input is the initially generated CTI and the output is a detailed analysis of each object of the CTI.

To achieve this, a vector database was developed to store preprocessed STIX schemas for all STIX SDOs, SCOs, and SROs. The database was implemented using the Chroma database [16]. As an embedding model, we use SentenceBERT (SBERT) [17], and more specifically the *sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2* model [18]. This allows to convert the STIX schemas into searchable embeddings for efficient retrieval and comparison with the generated CTI.

The publicly available STIX schema is though highly complex and contains numerous cross-references to other schema components. If this full schema were used as-is, the component would struggle to process and validate CTI because it would need to consider multiple dependencies for a single STIX object. To address this challenge, a preprocessing step was conducted to simplify the STIX schema before it was incorporated into the vector database. All cross-references, enumerated value dependencies, and indirect schema links were removed, allowing each STIX object schema to function independently. Once the database was developed, each STIX object in the CTI was queried against its corresponding simplified schema to systematically assess the presence of required and optional properties and detect syntactic inconsistencies.

C. CTI-GEN Updatable CTI Generator Component

This component updates the generated CTI, ensuring that it meets STIX compliance. The input to this component is the initially generated CTI annotated with missing attributes and syntax errors, and the output is a refined CTI with all required attributes including relevant optional attributes.

To achieve this, a prompt engineering procedure is utilized to provide detailed instructions to the model about the attributes that need to be added to the CTI according to the results of the *CTI-GEN Completeness & Syntactic Evaluator*. First, the prompt instructs the model to update the objects with any required attribute identified as missing by the *CTI-GEN Completeness & Syntactic Evaluator*. Then, the

model is instructed to incorporate missing optional attributes not included in the initially generated CTI, as identified by the *CTI-GEN Completeness & Syntactic Evaluator*. To add optional attributes, a structured approach is followed: attributes are included only if their values can be directly matched within the input text. If an exact match is unavailable, the model attempts to include partially matched or inferred values that can be logically deduced from the input text. By enriching the CTI with additional optional attributes, the generated CTI becomes more comprehensive, capturing a broader range of threat-related information available in the textual report.

Apart from adding missing attributes, this component evaluates the relationships among STIX objects in the CTI. Inconsistencies or missing relationships are corrected to ensure logical coherence within the generated intelligence.

Finally, the component is responsible for addressing any syntactic errors detected by the *CTI-GEN Completeness & Syntactic Evaluator* component. After all modifications are applied, the updated CTI is revalidated against the vector database to confirm that all required fields are present.

D. CTI-GEN Relationships Updating Editor Component

The *CTI-GEN Relationships Updating Editor* component is responsible for augmenting the generated CTI with additional STIX-defined relationships that were not initially established. This component does not modify existing relationships in the CTI bundle; instead, it focuses on identifying and adding new relationships. The input to this component is the previously updated CTI and the output is an enhanced CTI bundle with newly identified and valid STIX relationships.

The STIX specification defines various relationships that may exist between objects in a CTI. To incorporate additional relationships, a special prompt was designed to guide the LLM in establishing valid connections. This prompt was based on preprocessed STIX relationship mappings, as analysed in [15] that refined and restructured complex relationship definitions. For example, an original STIX relationship, such as *attack-pattern uses "malware, tool"*, is split into two distinct relationships: *attack-pattern uses malware* and *attack-pattern uses tool*. In addition, inverse relationships were considered, e.g., a tool using an attack-pattern, rather than just an attack-pattern using a tool. To evaluate the generated relationships, we perform a semantic search procedure in a database containing the preprocessed STIX relationships. We use the same embedding model as mentioned above. As a distance metric, we use cosine similarity to determine the semantic similarity between the existing STIX relationships and the newly identified ones.

E. CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker Component

The *CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker* component ensures the accuracy and validity of the values assigned to attributes within each STIX object in the generated CTI. Its primary function is to verify that the LLM does not introduce hallucinated or incorrect values. The input to this component is the previously enhanced CTI and the initial textual report, while the output is a refined version in which only meaningful and verifiable values and attributes are retained.

During this process, the LLM is provided with explicit instructions to evaluate all assigned values in the attributes of each STIX object in the CTI against the textual report. If a value for a required attribute cannot be directly matched, partially matched, or inferred from the input text, the entire object is removed to maintain STIX adherence. In the case of optional attributes, if a value cannot be validated in the same manner, only the specific property is removed from the object, and the rest of the object remains intact. This ensures that only verifiable threat intelligence is retained in the final CTI.

Certain attributes within STIX objects, specifically *tool_types*, *malware_types*, *indicator_types*, *infrastructure_type*, and *threat_actor_types*, are constrained to predefined lists of values. If a value initially assigned by the model is not explicitly mentioned in the text, the LLM attempts to select an alternative value from the predefined list for each attribute. If no suitable match can be found, the value is assigned the value "unknown". However, if the value was originally set to "unknown", it is excluded from further evaluation to avoid unnecessary modifications.

Additionally, some attributes within STIX objects are not derived from the input text and must be handled differently. These include *spec_version*, *id*, *created*, *modified*, *is_family*, and *type*. The *spec_version* is always set to 2.1, while the *id* is automatically generated as a UUID. The *created* attribute records the specific timestamp when the object was generated, and the *modified* attribute logs any subsequent updates. The *is_family* attribute is inferred programmatically rather than extracted from the text, while the *type* attribute is always assigned the value "bundle". Since these properties do not rely on textual input, the model is explicitly instructed to exclude them from the hallucination evaluation process.

F. CTI-GEN Syntactic Validator Component

The *CTI-GEN Syntactic Validator* Component is the final step in the framework, ensuring that the generated CTI is free from syntactic errors and that each STIX object fully adheres to its corresponding STIX schema. The input to this component is the CTI produced after the hallucination-checking process, and the output is a fully validated and syntactically correct CTI bundle that complies with STIX. During the previous evaluation steps, inconsistencies were observed in the LLM's generation of UUIDs for STIX objects. Multiple test runs revealed variability in UUID generation, highlighting the stochastic nature of LLM-generated outputs. This inconsistency led to incorrect identifier formatting, which is

critical for ensuring interoperability and compliance in STIX-based threat intelligence systems. To address these issues and guarantee full syntactic correctness, a validation procedure was implemented in the final stage of CTI generation. This procedure systematically verifies the format and structure of all STIX objects, ensuring that each UUID is generated correctly and that the overall CTI remains valid according to STIX.

IV. CTI-GEN FRAMEWORK DEMONSTRATION

We demonstrate the CTI-GEN Framework using the GPT-4o model to generate STIX-compliant CTI bundles.

A. CTI-GEN Initial CTI Generator Implementation

As described, the *CTI-GEN Initial CTI Generator* component generates the original CTI. The task presented to the LLM is stated verbatim as follows: "Generate a complete and valid STIX 2.1 CTI bundle based on the provided text description, instructions, and examples. Ensure the output adheres to the STIX 2.1 specification and includes all relevant SDOs, SCOs, and SROs. Detailed instructions about the objects creation and the required format are also provided (see Figure 2).

```
*Instructions:*
1. *Object Creation:*
  - Identify and create all relevant SDOs, SCOs, and SROs from the input text.
  - Each SDO and SCO must be a distinct object.
  - Ensure all objects are derived directly from the input text. Do not create objects that cannot be inferred from the text.

2. *Object Properties:*
  - Include all required and optional properties for each SDO and SCO as specified in the STIX 2.1 standard.

3. *Output Format:*
  - The final output must be a valid JSON object in the following format:
  ""json
  {{
    "type": "bundle",
    ...
  }}
```

Fig. 2. CTI-GEN Initial CTI Generator instructions

Figure 3 depicts a part of the generated CTI. The object concerns the malware "ShadowWorm" and contains different required and optional fields, such as "type", "spec_version", "id", "created", "modified", "name", and "description". Among the generated objects and based on the input text, five relationships were established: "attack-pattern"- "uses"- "vulnerability", "malware"- "uses"- "directory", "malware"- "uses"- "process", "attack-pattern"- "targets"- "identity" and "attack-pattern"- "uses"- "tool". An example of a relationship between the attack-pattern and the tool objects is provided in Figure 4. This relationship indicates that an attack pattern uses a tool to achieve its objective. In general, relationship objects also include required and optional attributes from the STIX specification.

B. CTI-GEN Completeness & Syntactic Evaluator Implementation

This component performs an initial validation of the generated CTI. For example, the following results demonstrate the evaluation outcomes for the malware object malware-f3b3c3e9-8f3b-4c3e-9f3b-2f3b4c3e9f3b:

```

1 {
2   "type": "malware",
3   "spec_version": "2.1",
4   "id": "malware--f3b3c3e9-8f3b-4c3e-9f3b-2f3b4c3e9f3b",
5   "created": "2024-05-05T00:00:00.000Z",
6   "modified": "2024-05-05T00:00:00.000Z",
7   "name": "ShadowWorm",
8   "description": "Malware facilitating communication with\
9     remote systems and executing commands as an elevated user."
10 }

```

Fig. 3. Malware Object

```

1 {
2   "type": "relationship",
3   "spec_version": "2.1",
4   "id": "relationship--c3e9f3b3-8f3b-4c3e-9f3b-2f3b4c3e9f3b",
5   "created": "2024-05-05T00:00:00.000Z",
6   "modified": "2024-05-05T00:00:00.000Z",
7   "relationship_type": "uses",
8   "source_ref": "attack-pattern--f3b3c3e9-8f3b-4c3e-9f3b-2f3b4c3e9f3b",
9   "target_ref": "tool--c3e9f3b3-8f3b-4c3e-9f3b-2f3b4c3e9f3b"
10 }

```

Fig. 4. Attack-pattern-Tool Relationship

```

1 {
2   "type": "malware",
3   "spec_version": "2.1",
4   "id": "malware--f3b3c3e9-8f3b-4c3e-9f3b-2f3b4c3e9f3b",
5   "created": "2024-05-05T00:00:00.000Z",
6   "modified": "2024-05-05T00:00:00.000Z",
7   "name": "ShadowWorm",
8   "description": "Malware facilitating communication with\
9     remote systems and executing commands as an elevated user.",
10   "malware_types": ["remote-access-trojan"],
11   "lang": "en"
12 }

```

Fig. 5. Updated Malware Object

- **Total required fields:** 6
- **Required fields included:** 5
- **Required fields list:** ['type', 'spec_version', 'id', 'created', 'modified', 'malware_types']
- **Missing required fields:** ['malware_types']
- **Optional fields included:** ['description', 'name']
- **Missing optional fields:** ['last_seen', 'lang', 'first_seen', 'confidence', 'revoked', 'sample_refs', 'external_references', 'os_execution_envs', 'labels', 'architecture_execution_envs', 'implementation_languages', 'capabilities', 'created_by_ref', 'is_family', 'aliases', 'kill_chain_phases']

The evaluation results indicate that one required attribute was missing from the initially generated object; the optional attributes that are included as well as those that are not present are also specified.

C. CTI-GEN Updatable CTI Generator Implementation

Next, the *CTI-GEN Updatable CTI generator*, responsible for updating the initial CTI based on the results of the previous component, provides the following task to the LLM: *"Your task is to **update the existing CTI report** using the information provided in the required fields JSON and Missing Optional Fields. Do NOT generate a new CTI from scratch. Instead, modify the initial CTI to incorporate new data, resolve*

*validation errors, and ensure compliance with the specified guidelines. **Ensure that any optional fields already present in the initial CTI are not deleted.**"*

The malware object after the updating procedure is depicted in Figure 5. To evaluate its correctness, the newly generated object was queried against the STIX schema database. The results of the evaluation are:

- **Total required fields:** 6
- **Required fields included:** 6
- **Required fields list:** ['type', 'spec_version', 'id', 'created', 'modified', 'malware_types']
- **Missing required fields:** ['None']
- **Optional fields included:** ['lang', 'description', 'name']
- **Missing optional fields:** ['last_seen', 'first_seen', 'confidence', 'revoked', 'sample_refs', 'external_references', 'os_execution_envs', 'labels', 'architecture_execution_envs', 'implementation_languages', 'capabilities', 'created_by_ref', 'is_family', 'aliases', 'kill_chain_phases']

The result shows that the model has incorporated the required field (i.e. "malware_types") that was initially missing. Also, the model has included a new optional field that was not in the initial CTI. No validation errors were found.

D. CTI-GEN Relationships Updating Editor Implementation

To encourage the model to establish more relationships between the objects of the CTI, we introduced new pairs of relationships derived from STIX that could exist between them. Specifically, the task provided to the model is: *Your task is to **update the existing Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) report** by adding new relationships from the list below. Ensure that the existing CTI structure, objects, and relationships are preserved, and only add the new relationships that are relevant and do not already exist in the CTI (i.e., are relevant to the existing objects)*. By providing this new knowledge, the model produces the following additional relationships: "attack-pattern"- "uses"- "malware" and "vulnerability"- "targeted by"- "attack-pattern". As an example the model was capable to produce valid instances of the above relationships, i.e., the attack-pattern 'Remote File Copy' uses the malware 'ShadowWorm', and the 'vulnerability CVE-2024-6789' is targeted by the 'attack-pattern'. The addition of these new relationships made the CTI more robust and comprehensive by generating more connections between the objects.

E. CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker Implementation

One of the most critical components of the proposed framework is the *CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker*, which evaluates the values of different attributes in CTI objects. An example evaluation outcome for the malware object is given below.

Malware Object

- **name:** "ShadowWorm"
Found: Yes, present in the input text.

- **description:** "Malware facilitating communication with remote systems and executing commands as an elevated user."

Found: Yes, present in the input text.

- **malware_types:** "remote-access-trojan"

Found: Yes, inferred from the description.

- **lang:** "en"

Found: Yes, assumed as default language.

The results indicate that some values were extracted directly from the input text, whereas others were inferred. Notably, the model did not evaluate the optional fields even though at the beginning of the evaluation it stated otherwise. However, across different iterations, all values were eventually evaluated. This behavior arises from the stochastic nature of LLMs.

F. CTI-GEN Syntactic Validator Implementation

As noted earlier, the framework does not always generate consistent UUIDs. For example, the correct ID for the malware object should follow this format: malware--[0-9a-fA-F]{8}-[0-9a-fA-F]{4}-[1-5][0-9a-fA-F]{3}-[89abAB][0-9a-fA-F]{3}-[0-9a-fA-F]{12}. I.e., the id must start with "malware-" followed by a UUID in a specific format. The UUID must follow the format 8-4-4-4-12 hexadecimal characters with hyphens. The first digit of the third group must be 1-5 while the first digit of the fourth group must be 8, 9, a, b, A, or B. However, the model produced the UUID: malware--e3b0c442-98fc-cc14-9afb4c8996f, which is incorrect as the third group cc14 does not follow the pattern: the first character should be 1-5, but it was a 'c'.

To deal with the stochastic nature of LLMs and solve the problem of incorrect UUID generation, we developed a Python code procedure to generate correct UUIDs for different objects. For example, after executing the proposed code, the malware object takes the following UUID: malware--e7e1d0d5-1610-4813-87e3-aeaaa34a5a18. The generated UUID is correct because it begins with the required prefix malware and follows the 8-4-4-4-12 hexadecimal format. The third group is 4813, where the first character is within the allowed range of 1-5, and the fourth group is 87e3, where the first character is one of the allowed values (8, 9, a, b, A, or B).

V. EVALUATION

Three evaluations were performed: (i) on the objects that the model generates, (ii) on the correctness of the relationships between the objects, and (iii) on the accuracy of the value assignment to the attributes of the objects. The evaluations are reported in detail in the following subsections.

Despite careful investigation to identify a universally accepted ground truth, we found no existing standardized dataset with annotated STIX objects. As a result, we constructed our own dataset by manually creating 15 examples that describe attack scenarios. Then, for each of these examples, we identified entities that could be mapped to STIX objects. Through these examples, we covered the entire spectrum of STIX objects.

The following metrics were used: **True Positives (TP):** Results (i.e., objects, relationships, assigned values) identified by the LLM, matching the ground truth. **False Positives (FP):** Results identified by the LLM, but not present in the ground truth. **False Negatives (FN):** Results in the ground truth that the LLM failed to identify. **Precision:** Proportion of correctly identified results. **Recall:** Proportion of the ground truth correctly identified by the LLM. **F1 Score:** A single metric balancing precision and recall.

A. Objects Generation Evaluation

Table I presents the evaluation results for object generation for the 15 input texts. For instance, the first example should contain the following six objects as identified by two experts in our team: "network-traffic", "vulnerability", "ipv4-addr", "mac-addr", "intrusion-set", and "tool". The model identified the following eight objects: "threat-actor", "campaign", "vulnerability", "tool", "infrastructure", "ipv4-addr", "mac-addr", "network-traffic". I.e., the LLM generated three additional

TABLE I
EVALUATION RESULTS OF LLM-BASED CTI GENERATION: OBJECTS

Example	Correct Objects - Manually Identified	Additional Objects - Automatically Identified	Correct Additional Identified Objects (Expert 1 Assessment)	Correct Additional Identified Objects (Expert 2 Assessment)	Ground Truth	Identified Objects	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
1	6	3	2	2	8	8	7	1	1	0.88	0.88	0.88
2	6	2	2	2	8	8	8	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00
3	5	2	0	0	5	6	4	2	1	0.67	0.80	0.73
4	6	1	1	1	7	7	7	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00
5	6	0	0	0	6	4	4	0	2	1.00	0.67	0.80
6	6	2	0	0	6	5	3	2	3	0.60	0.50	0.55
7	7	0	0	0	7	7	7	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00
8	5	1	0	0	5	4	3	1	1	0.75	0.75	0.75
9	6	1	0	0	6	5	4	1	2	0.80	0.67	0.73
10	6	2	0	0	6	5	3	2	4	0.60	0.43	0.50
11	6	3	3	3	9	6	6	0	3	1.00	0.67	0.80
12	6	2	2	2	8	7	7	0	1	1.00	0.88	0.93
13	6	1	1	1	7	7	7	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00
14	6	1	0	0	6	5	5	1	2	0.83	0.71	0.77
15	7	1	0	0	7	6	5	1	2	0.83	0.71	0.77
Mean										86%	78%	81%

TABLE II
EVALUATION RESULTS OF LLM-BASED CTI GENERATION: RELATIONSHIPS

	Example															Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	
# Generated Relationships	10	3	8	8	4	4	7	4	5	5	7	8	7	3	4	
TP	3	0	6	5	0	4	4	4	1	5	3	6	4	2	3	
FP	7	3	2	3	4	0	3	0	4	0	4	2	3	1	1	
Precision	0.30	0.00	0.75	0.62	0.00	1.00	0.57	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.43	0.75	0.57	0.67	0.75	57%

objects, namely the "threat-actor", "campaign", and "infrastructure". Upon review, the two experts identified as correct the "infrastructure" and "campaign", which became part of the ground truth, along with the six objects that were initially manually identified by the experts, resulting in a total of eight objects in the ground truth. Moreover, the model could not identify one of the objects initially identified by the experts, namely the "intrusion-set" object. The results showed an F1-score of 81%, indicating a good balance between reliability and completeness.

The mean precision for all the examples was 86% indicating that when the model generates an object, it is almost always correct. The mean recall of 78% indicates that the model correctly identified many objects, but not all expected ground truth elements. Finally, the mean F1-score of 81% reflects a balanced performance, although it suggests that improvements in recall could enhance the overall effectiveness. One crucial characteristic of the evaluation is the presence of the two human experts in the categorization of the newly identified objects, who completely agreed on their assessments.

B. Relationships Generation Evaluation

The next step was to evaluate the relationships generated among the objects in the CTI. For comprehensive and useful CTI, the model must be able to generate meaningful relationships between objects. As discussed, we performed a semantic search procedure during the evaluation and made six observations based on the results. (1) Some model-generated relationships exactly match the STIX schemas relationships, i.e., both the objects of a relationship and the verb between them are identical. (2) Some model-generated relationships had the same objects as the STIX schema, but with slight variations in the verb; e.g., instead of "use," the model might generate "uses". (3) There were instances where the objects of the relationships remained the same as in the STIX schema, but the verb was entirely different. (4) There were cases where one object and the verb remained the same as in the STIX schema, while the other object changed. (5) In some cases, only one object in the relationship matched the STIX schema, while the verb and the other object were different. (6) There were cases where neither the objects nor the verb in the model-generated relationship had any relation to those in the STIX schema. In this work, we considered as correct only the relationships belonging to the first two observations.

As depicted in Table II, many relationships were generated from the different input examples. The 57% Precision shows that the model is capable of extracting some valuable relation-

ships between the different objects. However, a significant portion of relationships were not related to STIX. In future work, we plan to take into account in our evaluation the relationships belonging to the other four observations categories and update accordingly the STIX specification, as STIX includes some predefined objects, but also allows the incorporation of new objects.

C. Attributes Values Assignment Evaluation

During the construction of the objects, the model assigns values to their attributes. However, during the assignment of these values, the model might hallucinate by assigning values not present in the input text. The *CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker* component evaluates the values of the different attributes, but there are cases where it may not evaluate all available attributes. The human experts evaluated how many attributes were correctly populated with values among the ones evaluated by the *CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker*, indicating a correct behavior from the model, and how many were wrongly populated, indicating hallucinations.

The evaluation results are depicted in Table III. In some examples (e.g., examples #8-#11), the framework evaluated (through its *CTI-GEN Hallucination Checker*) all the required and optional attributes. In other cases, though, the model failed to evaluate all attribute values, despite being provided with detailed instructions, and/or performed the evaluation on some attributes that was instructed to avoid. This increases the difficulty of a complete CTI evaluation and that is why our experts focused only on the attributes evaluated by the model and precision was calculated based on them.

For these evaluated attributes, the high precision indicated that for many of them, the value assignment was correct. E.g., for the attribute-value pair: *Attack Pattern Object*: - name: "Passive Network Mapping", the evaluation was: "- Evaluation: Found in input text. - Action: Keep the object intact". This indicates that the model correctly fully matched the value "Passive Network Mapping" in the input text and assigned it to the required attribute "name" of the "Attack Pattern Object".

In another example, for the attribute-value pair: *sectors*: "technology", the evaluation was the following: "- Evaluation: Found in input text as "technology services." - Action: Update to "technology services". The model performed a partial matching evaluation and found the initially assigned value in a broader setting (i.e., as part of a two-words phrase).

The model was also able to identify incorrect value assignments. For example, for the attribute-value pair: *value*: "192.0.2.1" of object *IPv4-Addr*, the evaluation was: "- Found

TABLE III
EVALUATION RESULTS OF LLM-BASED CTI GENERATION: VALUES
ASSIGNMENT TO ATTRIBUTES

Example	# Objects generated	# Attributes	# Attributes Evaluated (Hallucination Checker)	% Attributes evaluated (Hallucination Checker)	# Correct evaluated attributes (Expert 1 assessment)	# Correct evaluated attributes (Expert 2 assessment)	# Correct & evaluated attributes	TP	FP	Precision
1	8	41	22	0.54	22	22	22	22	0	1.00
2	8	36	27	0.75	27	27	27	27	0	1.00
3	6	50	54	1.00	54	54	54	54	0	1.00
4	7	40	35	0.88	35	35	35	35	0	1.00
5	4	21	22	1.00	22	22	22	22	0	1.00
6	5	51	43	0.84	43	43	43	43	0	1.00
7	7	24	24	1.00	24	24	24	24	0	1.00
8	4	40	40	1.00	36	36	36	36	4	0.90
9	5	20	20	1.00	18	18	18	18	2	0.90
10	5	33	33	1.00	33	33	33	33	0	1.00
11	6	22	22	1.00	22	22	22	22	0	1.00
12	7	45	39	0.87	39	39	39	39	0	1.00
13	7	51	60	1.00	60	60	60	60	0	1.00
14	5	77	71	0.93	71	71	71	71	0	1.00
15	6	47	49	1.00	37	37	37	37	12	0.75
Mean				96.41%						96%

in input text: No - Action: Remove the object as the required field value is not found". Here, the model reflects on its initial decision to build an IPv4-Addr object. Given that the value of the required attribute could not be found or inferred from the input text, the model deleted the object.

Overall, the model performed well in value assignment and was able to identify incorrect values. However, some attributes were not evaluated, which affects the completeness of the evaluation. Moreover, the occurrence of false positives highlights the importance of human involvement in the evaluation process, namely in the assessment of the accuracy of the generated CTI. Although experts were involved in the evaluation process, their subjective judgments may add bias. However, since the LLM provided detailed and structured analysis for its outputs, this bias was mitigated, as the experts could objectively verify whether the assigned values were justified based on the input textual report.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work introduced the novel CTI-GEN framework for generating STIX compliant CTI using LLMs. The proposed framework addresses critical challenges in CTI generation, such as the limited adoption of STIX and the currently incomplete and erroneous CTI produced. The framework consists of six main components that ensure the generation of high-quality CTI. Experimental results using GPT-4o demonstrated the framework's capability to generate complete and syntactically

valid CTI, which can also operate at scale with large amounts of input. Future enhancements could focus on broadening the available input to include large PDF files containing threat reports and raw log data captured by honeypots, and also designing novel architectures using LLM agents for improved performance. Knowledge Graphs could also be used to provide reasoning and explainability to the language models.

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